

Demonstration of Multi-Tenant Optical Transport Network Slicing with T-API

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Abstract—Network slicing is crucial to meet the diverse requirements of modern telecommunication services. At the transport level, it enables the creation of dedicated virtual networks on a shared optical infrastructure, providing customized solutions for different service providers operating on this optical network. This paper explores the integration of optical transport network slicing using the Transport API (T-API) in a real-world optical network infrastructure. T-API increases the programmability of optical systems and improves flexibility and interoperability in network management. In particular, we demonstrate that the latest enhancements to T-API now enable straightforward partitioning of optical networks, helping service providers to manage their own slices independently without introducing added complexities. Our study showcases T-API’s effectiveness in a small-scale optical network, where customisers can provide and tailor end-to-end connectivity services. This proof-of-concept highlights the potential of T-API to provide standardized, efficient, and scalable control of increasingly complex multi-tenant optical network resources.

Index Terms—Network Slicing, Multi-Tenant Transport Networks, Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Transport API (T-API)

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of new 5G services and applications, ranging from remote healthcare solutions to augmented reality experiences, has necessitated a fundamental shift in telecommunications network architecture. To accommodate the diverse requirements of these services, the concept of network slicing gained prominence [1], [2].

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Network slicing involves creating dedicated virtual networks, or network slices, on a shared physical infrastructure. These network slices, operating across multi-domain and multi-technology networks, provide tailored solutions for each specific 5G service, ensuring its resource guarantees. As the demand for diverse 5G services continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to also integrate a more responsive control of the underlying optical network when managing the overall end-to-end slice [3].

Concurrently, the expanding interest in open optical networks, characterized by the decoupling of software and hardware through open application programming interfaces (API), has provided network operators with a more flexible framework for managing network infrastructure [4]. The Transport API (T-API), developed by the Open Networking Foundation (ONF), has emerged as the industry standard. T-API exports the programmability of optical systems to software-defined networking (SDN) controllers, preventing “vendor islands” where one vendor provides all optical solutions [5]. For transport network operators, adopting T-API offers flexibility and interoperability in provisioning dynamic transport network slices [6].

In this paper, we demonstrate the capabilities of T-API in an existing optical network infrastructure consisting of four transponders. Utilizing T-API, different network slices are exposed to different customers, allowing them to tailor their slice to their specific needs while sharing the same optical infrastructure. Through this demo, our aim is to provide standardized, efficient, and scalable control of optical network resources, paving the way for fully customized end-to-end network slicing.

Our paper starts with a description of the transport net-

work slicing architecture in Section II, highlighting the role of the network orchestrator and the integration of T-API. Section III continues with a practical demonstration of optical network slicing using T-API within a small-scale optical network, showcasing how different network slices can be effectively managed and provisioned.

II. TRANSPORT NETWORK SLICING ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we present a multi-tenant 5G network slicing architecture that dynamically delivers virtual 5G network slices tailored to each specific tenant requirements [7]. We focus on transport network slicing, more specifically on partitioning the shared optical transport network for different tenants or customers, who, in this context, are service providers. This architecture includes SDN control instances that allow each tenant to fully manage its allocated virtual resources. Figure 1 provides an illustrative overview of how the optical network is partitioned, then exposed and managed by several service providers. The details of this architecture will be further discussed in this section.

A. Mapping Customer Requirements to Transport Network Slices

In our architecture, service providers play a central role in offering a diverse range of services to end customers, including both businesses and residential users. These service providers typically own IP/MPLS infrastructure and may also have their own optical infrastructure in certain areas. However, in locations where they lack optical infrastructure, service providers have the option to hire part of the optical infrastructure from a shared optical infrastructure provider. This arrangement allows service providers to expand their service offerings and meet the growing demands of their customers.

To ensure that service providers can effectively meet the needs of their customers, network slicing comes into play. Network slicing is a proposed approach for a single network to support services with different operational parameters and policies [8]. Fundamentally, the network is viewed as an asset pool of physical network resources, virtual network functions (VNFs), connectivity, bandwidth, and computing power. A network slice combines these assets into a virtual network partition. In the context of our architecture, we focus primarily on the transport network slices. These slices act as a bridge connecting the access and core network segments of a 5G End-to-End (E2E) slicing service, as described by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). The upper part of Figure 1 depicts the customer applications interacting with their service provider's network orchestrator, which

coordinates the provisioning and management of the transport network slice to meet the specific requirements of the customer.

B. Software-Defined Transport Network Orchestrator

For each tenant or service provider, the network orchestrator plays a crucial role in managing various network services across domains and layers. As the central interface between operational systems and the underlying network infrastructure, the orchestrator coordinates services and maintains a comprehensive, multi-layer and multi-domain view of its network topology. The technological domain represented in Figure 1 is an IP-over-Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing (DWDM) transport network, consisting of two layers: packet and optical. Each layer is managed by its respective SDN controller. The packet layer contains IP routers, while the optical layer consists of reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs) connected by optical fiber links. Each IP router is connected to a ROADM via a pluggable transceiver to provide traffic grooming capabilities at each node. While the optical infrastructure is shared among multiple tenants, each tenant's IP infrastructure remains isolated within their respective network slices.

The primary function of the network orchestrator is to facilitate service coordination across these multiple domains and layers. This requires seamless collaboration with both IP and optical controllers, using a standardized protocol for sharing and visualizing network topology details [9]. The information collected from the IP and optical layers is combined in a multilayer topology database, along with the mapping between IP and optical nodes.

Tenants are provided with programmable APIs to manage their slices, allowing them full control over their allocated resources. The internal sharing of information within the network orchestrator allows it to make rapid decisions when handling traffic intents, guiding the network to optimal performance. To further enhance the management experience, a user interface (UI) displaying the information collected by the network orchestrator provides a clear view of the virtual network topology, the status of the slice's assets, and other critical data. This allows tenants to effectively control their allocated resources.

C. Optical Network Partitioning using Open Data Models

As optical networks expand and become more complex, they become increasingly segmented to improve manageability. One such segment is managed by the

Fig. 1: Proposed architecture for enabling network slicing over optical networks using T-API.

SDN controller of the shared optical infrastructure, also known as the open Optical Line System (OLS) SDN controller. If this OLS SDN controller provided proprietary interfaces to a network orchestrator, it would make network slicing challenging and expensive, as each interface would require a dedicated plug-in. The proposed approach to network slicing is therefore based on open and standard data models. Standardized, modular data models address these challenges by abstracting the underlying transport network and its components, such as ports, links, directions, and other parameters. This abstraction simplifies the network slicing design by facilitating the partitioning of the optical network infrastructure and allowing the allocation of a subset of resources to a specific instance.

To achieve this, we make use of the Transport API (T-API) on the northbound interface of the OLS controller, which serves as the industry-standard interface linking the service provider's optical SDN controller and the OLS controller [10]. In particular, the latest T-API release, equipped with support for the photonic media layer (i.e., continuous optical spectrum along a path in the WDM layer), is of interest for optical network slicing. Additionally, the enhanced capabilities of T-API now allow for straightforward partitioning of optical networks, using unique endpoints for each service provider, which significantly simplifies the process. T-API offers a range of services:

- *Common Context*: The T-API context serves as a shared repository of information between a T-API client (a network orchestrator managing its own partition), and the T-API server (the optical SDN controller). This model organizes the optical domain by means of Service Interface-Points (SIP), identifiable by their universally unique identifiers (UUID), providing endpoints between which services can be deployed. A basic task for a network orchestrator is to retrieve its context and access its SIPs, allowing the request of connectivity services. To logically separate the different network partitions, the context for each network partition is defined by a UUID and can be retrieved by making a call with this UUID as endpoint on the T-API server.
- *Topology Context*: If a given T-API server supports the topology model, it augments the T-API context with an inventory of one or more topologies. Each topology consists of a collection of nodes, equipped with Node Edge Points (NEPs). These can be further divided into internal and external NEPs. Internal NEPs are connected by links within the topology, while external NEPs interface with SIPs provided to the client. For the terminal devices, a logical association is created between a client (transceiver) port and an optical channel linked to the line port of the device.
- *Connectivity Service*: This model extends the com-

Fig. 2: Visual representation of two distinct virtual network partitions extracted from the shared CTTC optical network infrastructure, including their spectrum resources.

mon context to facilitate the instantiation of connections or in-slice services. To this end, Connection End Points (CEPs) are configured over the external NEPs. A simple operation involves requesting a connectivity service between two SIPs to set up a point-to-point connection. The optical controller then executes the required logic to perform per-device configuration, which includes the provisioning of a Network Media Channel (NMC) between two terminal devices.

By using T-API, we ensure a seamless and efficient implementation of network slices, enabling tenants to manage their allocated resources effectively while maintaining interoperability across multi-vendor environments.

III. OPTICAL TRANSPORT NETWORK SLICING WITH T-API: A PROOF-OF-CONCEPT

In this section, we demonstrate the practical application of optical network slicing using T-API within an actual, small-scale optical network infrastructure. This network, managed by the CTTC research institution, is situated in the Barcelona metropolitan area, and composed as depicted in the left part of Figure 1. The network comprises four ROADM devices, interconnected by ten unidirectional single-mode fibers (SMF) operating on DWDM channels within the C-band spectrum. Of these links, eight adhere to a fixed International Telecom-

munication Union (ITU) grid, featuring either 50 GHz or 100 GHz channel spacing. The remaining two links utilize a flexible ITU grid, allowing dynamic adjustment of channel spacing.

In this test, the infrastructure supports the creation of two distinct virtual network partitions, each uniquely defined by a UUID. These two partitions are logically isolated from one another and enable different clients or service providers to manage their respective partition independently, which is further described below.

A. Retrieving a Network Partition's Internal T-API Context

The optical CTTC controller uses various REST-based API operations to manage its internal T-API context, providing a comprehensive view of the entire optical network, organized as mentioned in Section II-C. Through T-API, the controller supplies two virtual optical partitions, each representing a subset of network resources, made available to two clients (service providers). These two partitions and their individual resources are visualized in Figure 2. This partitioning is enabled by T-API endpoints, where each partition is identified by a unique UUID. For instance, the endpoint `http://10.8.0.1:4900/42efa4b0-05a4-5984-9b6d-d0d7aa1f3a97/restconf/data/T-API-common:context` uses UUID `42efa4b0-05a4-5984-9b6d-d0d7aa1f3a97` to designate a specific network partition. This allows clients to manage their allocated resources with simple HTTP request methods to these dedicated T-API endpoints.

Accordingly, the client initially needs to know the IP address and port of the involved optical CTTC controller. This controller (with IP and port, e.g., 10.8.0.2 and 4900 respectively) and client are connected over the public Internet via tunnels. Upon request, the network orchestrator can then retrieve the T-API context, which includes the virtual network topology consisting of nodes, links, and NEPs, along with the client's SIPs and a list of active connections (services). These SIPs are associated with one or multiple client port NEPs in the transponders, facilitating connectivity requests. For testing purposes, a user interface is used to help visualize all this content.

B. Configuring In-Slice Services per Network Partition

In this section, we describe the steps involved in provisioning an end-to-end connectivity service between two DWDM transceivers. The goal is to ensure that clients have full control over the management of their own network slice. To initiate this process, the client must specify several key parameters: the source and

```

{
  "tapi-connectivity:connectivity-service": [
    {
      "uuid": "af7e1ec7-dc51-478d-8f9e-77748fb040fb",
      "connectivity-constraint": {
        "requested-capacity": {
          "total-size": {
            "value": 50,
            "unit": "GHz"
          }
        }
      },
      "connectivity-direction": "UNIDIRECTIONAL"
    },
    {
      "end-point": [
        {
          "service-interface-point": {
            "service-interface-point-uuid": "0ef74f99-1acc-57bd-ab9d-4b958b06c513"
          },
          "layer-protocol-name": "PHOTONIC_MEDIA",
          "layer-protocol-qualifier": "tapi-photonic-media:PHOTONIC_LAYER_QUALIFIER_NMC",
          "local-id": "0ef74f99-1acc-57bd-ab9d-4b958b06c513",
          "tapi-photonic-media:media-channel-connectivity-service-end-point-spec": {
            "mc-config": {
              "spectrum": {
                "frequency-constraint": {
                  "adjustment-granularity": "6_6_25GHZ",
                  "grid-type": "FLEX"
                },
                "lower-frequency": 193725000,
                "upper-frequency": 193775000
              }
            }
          }
        },
        {
          "service-interface-point": {
            "service-interface-point-uuid": "741daaae-8407-5404-b52f-cb442fb0cf6d"
          },
          "layer-protocol-name": "PHOTONIC_MEDIA",
          "layer-protocol-qualifier": "tapi-photonic-media:PHOTONIC_LAYER_QUALIFIER_NMC",
          "local-id": "741daaae-8407-5404-b52f-cb442fb0cf6d",
          "tapi-photonic-media:media-channel-connectivity-service-end-point-spec": {
            "mc-config": {
              "spectrum": {
                "frequency-constraint": {
                  "adjustment-granularity": "6_6_25GHZ",
                  "grid-type": "FLEX"
                },
                "lower-frequency": 193725000,
                "upper-frequency": 193775000
              }
            }
          }
        }
      ],
      "include-link": [
        "6e57eb11-cafa-5ca7-a79a-ba013f523900",
        "8547f812-8757-596d-b796-b2d0f6690dea"
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 3: A sample JSON payload for provisioning an end-to-end connectivity service.

destination Service Interface Points (SIPs), the desired directivity (unidirectional or bidirectional), and the required capacity (e.g., 50GHz). With this information, the CTTC controller performs a first-fit spectrum assignment on the shortest available path, if possible.

In addition to these basic parameters, clients can further customize the connection to suit their preferences. To do so, the network orchestrator first calculates the k -shortest paths and evaluates the available spectrum. Based on this information, the client can specify optional parameters: the frequency channel and grid type for the underlying optical connection, as well as an ordered set of links (fibers) to be used. These fields are encoded in a JSON payload, which is then sent to the optical CTTC controller via the dedicated REST interface, targeting the specific endpoint for the client's partition. In the event of a misconfigured

or incomplete request, the CTTC controller manages and resolves these issues, warning the client through appropriate error messages or notifications. The network orchestrator keeps track of all established connections via their UUIDs. When a client wants to stop a service, a client can send an HTTP DELETE request to the CTTC controller. As an example, to delete a service, the following endpoint is addressed: `http://10.8.0.1:4900/42efa4b0-05a4-5984-9b6d-d0d7aa1f3a97/restconf/data/T-API-common:context/T-API-connectivity:connectivity-context/connectivity-service={uuid}`.

To further illustrate the process, Figure 3 presents a typical JSON payload example for a provisioning request. This JSON payload is configured through a UI, which simplifies the process for clients. First, a random UUID is generated for the connectivity service request. In this instance, we consider a unidirectional service ("connectivity-service"), specifying a connection request that supports a 50GHz signal ("connectivity-constraint"). The network orchestrator tracks the available SIPs for the desired source and destination nodes, which are required for each of the two "end-point" entries. Additionally, the optional parameters for further customization include the "T-API-photonic-media:media-channel-connectivity-service-end-point-spec" section, where the frequency range and grid type are specified under the "mc-config" key. The UUIDs of the specific links (fibers) to be utilized are listed within the "include-link" key. By sending such JSON payloads to the optical CTTC controller, the client can ensure the performance and customization of their network slice.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we demonstrated the latest Transport API (T-API) capabilities that enable network slicing within an optical transport network. Our proof-of-concept illustrated how T-API can facilitate the creation and management of virtual network partitions, allowing service providers using this optical infrastructure to manage their slices autonomously without added complexity. This demonstration highlighted T-API's potential to offer streamlined and scalable control over multi-tenant optical network resources, emphasizing its role in the broader context of 5G network slicing.

Our future work will focus on key areas to further enhance the utility of optical transport network slicing. Firstly, we plan to explore multi-layer integration tests with the service provider's IP layer to align network operations and coordination. Additionally, we will work on automating and optimizing in-slice service allocation

based on the real-time network status. Implementing mechanisms that dynamically adjust resource allocation in response to network conditions, such as IP layer congestion, could further enhance service reliability and efficiency.

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